

Original Research

Non-linear Influence of Environmental Regulation on the Technological Innovation: The Moderating Effect of Media Attention

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Abstract

Coal mining firms in the bottleneck period of development are attempting to promote the transformation and upgrading with the strategy of technological innovation. Using a sample of coal mining firms listed on the Shanghai and Shenzhen Stock Exchanges in China from 2016 to 2022. The paper empirically investigates the relationship between environmental regulation (ER) and technological innovation (TI), and further tests the moderating effect of media attention (MA). We find that there is a U-shaped relationship between economic environmental regulation (EER) and the input capability of TI, with a single threshold effect. The same is true of relationship between EER and the output capability of TI. We also find that there is a U-shaped relationship between administrative environmental regulation (AER) and the transformation capability of TI, with double threshold effect. Additionally, MA strengthens the relationship between ER and TI, especially for negative MA, which confirms that media reports on environmental pollution can play a role in curbing environmental pollution. Our conclusions not only give a tentative theoretical analysis with regard to the relationship between ER and TI, but also provides a useful reference for the reform and development of coal mining industry.

Keywords: Environmental regulation, media attention, technological innovation.

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Introduction

Since the reform and opening up more than 40 years ago, China's economy has undergone a transformation from rapid growth to steady growth. Due to the long-term extensive development, the ecological environment has been seriously damaged, especially in resource-based cities, where environmental pollution is a serious problem. At present, the intensive development of China's economic transformation and upgrading has become an urgent task. Protecting ecological environment and realizing the sustainability of economic development have attracted substantial interest from academic researchers. In order to effectively meet people's needs for a green and low-carbon ecological environment, the government departments have issued numerous laws and regulations, such as *Environmental Protection Law*, and *Outline of the National Strategy of Innovation-Driven Development*. Economic growth must not be at the expense of the ecological environment. The environmental protection needs the joint participation of the government, enterprises and the public.

The transformation and upgrading of traditional economy are naturally driven by the innovation strategy. According to media reports, innovation has been emphasized more than 50 times in the report of government meeting², which shows that innovation plays a critical role when China's economy is expected to achieve high-quality development. Enterprises occupy the dominant position in carrying out innovation activities. The economic development needs to rely on the implementation of innovation strategy. TI, as the core of innovation strategy, has exerted an important impact on the survival and development of enterprises. Coal mining firms have been labeled as "high energy consumption, high emission and high pollution" for a long period. The problems, such as backward production technology, high casualty rate among miners, as well as serious environmental pollution and destruction, are difficult to be solved in the short run. Coal is the basic energy for economic growth. If the substandard coal mining firms are just shut down, it is difficult to fundamentally help coal mining firms get rid of the predicament. To enhance the market competitiveness of coal mining firms and improve the quality of coal products, it is necessary to achieve an innovation-driven development mode, rather than a factor-driven one.

To extend and enrich the theoretical researches on TI and provide practical inspiration for policy-makers and corporate managers. Using the sample data of listed coal mining firms in China from 2016 to 2022, the study empirically investigates the impact of ER on TI and examines the moderating effect of MA. The contributions of the research from our perspective are attempted to summarize in several ways. First, there have been many studies on the impact of ER on TI, but scholars have different views. We also find that few studies focus on the coal mining firms to discuss the impact of ER on TI. Therefore, according to Following the Cost Hypothesis (CH) and Porter Hypothesis (PH) respectively, we focus on coal mining firms to investigate the impact of ER on TI, which provides empirical evidence for corporate managers to have a deep understanding of innovation activities in the new environment.

Second, most of studies related to TI measure the extent of TI from the perspective of

² The 19th national congress of the communist party of China (CPC).

R&D investment (Booth et al., 2006; Vithessonthi & Racela, 2016; Yang & Liao, 2017). The selection of proxy variable is too single to comprehensively estimate the TI. To explore the TI in a more comprehensive way, the study analyzes the TI from three perspectives, that is, input capability of TI, output capability of TI, and transformation capability of TI. This lays a theoretical foundation for the further research on TI.

Third, the existing researches have confirmed the governance effect of media, but these researches only analyze the company administration function of media coverage (Dyck & Zingales, 2008; Chen et al., 2010; Luo, 2012; Liu & Mcconnell, 2013). To further obtain empirical evidence from the impact of media coverage, the study explores the impact of MA on the relationship between ER and TI, which enriches the theoretical research on media governance and provides a crucial reference for government departments and corporate managers.

The rest of the study is arranged as follows. Literature review is in the second section. Research hypotheses are in the third section. The fourth section is the research design. This section presents the definition of variables, the sample used, and the model designed. Empirical research is in the fifth section. This section discusses the findings. The sixth section is the research conclusions.

Literature review

The TI process from the stage of R&D investment to achievement transformation is influenced by many factors; for instance, the impact effect of ER on TI has been widely concerned by scholars, but scholars have different views. First, ER is significantly and positively related to TI. The theoretical basis of this conclusion is Porter Hypothesis (PH), which holds that reasonably and effectively designed ER can facilitate innovation, which further leads to the improvement of production efficiency, the increase of operating profits, and enhancement of market competitiveness (Porter & van der Linde, 1995). Based on the above theories, scholars use empirical method to believe that ER promotes R&D investment, and generates an incentive effect on innovation activities (Whitford & Tucker, 2009; Kneller & Manderson, 2012). Second, ER is significantly and negatively correlated with TI. According to the traditional economic theory, strict ER, such as environmental tax, and emission quota, restrict firms' production and investment. Meanwhile, to meet the environmental standards, the expenses of pollution control not only increase the amortized cost of products, but also reduce the investment in R&D, which is not advantageous for the implementation of technology innovation activities (Palmer et al., 1995; Wagner, 2007; Rubashkina et al., 2015). Third, the relationship between ER and TI is uncertain. Domazlicky & Weber (2004) believe that there is no obvious evidence that ER leads to a decline in the technical efficiency of chemical industry. Kneller & Manderson (2012) find in their empirical study that ER has no significant effect on TI. In addition, Alpay et al. (2002) take the food industry of United States and Mexico as the research sample, and find that ER policies issued by the American government are negatively corrected with the productivity, while the Mexican ER policies can help improve the productivity.

In recent years, scholars have also paid attention to the correlation between ER and TI. Pan et al. (2021) tests the relationship between ER policy and cleaner production TI in

China, and find that ER policy is more conducive to cleaner production TI in heavy pollution industry. Feng and Chen (2023) takes Chinese new energy firms as a research sample, and argue that command-and-control ER and market investment-oriented ER are positively related to the green innovation. Manu et al. (2024) find that stronger ER can promote innovation by examining relevant data from 32 countries. Yu et al. (2024) find that direct ER are conducive to innovation in China's textile industry. However, Xie et al. (2022) find that ER can reduce the level of TI, because companies have less willingness to innovate. According to the research results in recent years, we find that more studies provide evidence to support that ER is beneficial to TI, but there are also studies that show that ER inhibits TI.

From the above existing studies, it can be seen that the impact effect of ER on TI may be different due to some factors such as research sample and time period. ER policy, as a formal external governance mechanism, will have a significant impact on TI. Therefore, it is of certain theoretical and practical value to study the correlation between ER and TI.

In addition, as an informal external governance tool, media are not only the vehicles for advertising, but also the mirrors reflecting the reality of corporate activities. Media have the functions of information transfer, direction of public opinion, and image building, which has a great deal of impact on corporate behaviors and many stakeholders (Fombrun & Shanley, 1990; Fiss & Zajac, 2006). Therefore, it is necessary to discuss the impact of MA on the correlation between ER and TI.

Research hypothesis

With the continuous advancement of China's industrialization, people's material wealth has been greatly enriched. However, while creating this material wealth, the ecological environment has been seriously damaged. For the coal mining industry, a large number of pollutants have been produced when coal is produced and consumed. In order to effectively curb environmental pollution, the relevant department has issued a number of ER.

ER refers to the measures taken by government departments to regulate the external diseconomy of corporate activities in order to achieve the coordination between economic growth and environmental protection, including environment concerned laws, regulations, and policies (Guo, 2006; Ye & Wang, 2019). As one of the industries with high energy consumption, high emission and high pollution, the intervention means of ER issued by government departments will greatly restrict the production and investment of coal mining firms. In the context of the increasingly high requirements of the public for environment, the impact of ER on the development of coal mining firms can't be ignored. To reduce the environmental pollution and improve the production technology, it is of necessity for coal mining firms to make strategic decisions on TI, which involves innovation in products, processes, marketing, and management (Gerwin & Barrowman, 2002 ; Badawy, 2009 ; Feng, 2013). Scholars put forward different views on the relationship between ER and TI, but there is no unanimous conclusion. According to the "following the CH", ER has a crowding-out effect on TI; that is, ER will increase the cost of corporate production and operation, and the cost of environmental governance, which squeezes investment in R&D (Gray & Shadbegian, 2003; Lanoie et al.,2008; Carballeira

et al., 2016). To be specific, under strict ER, the corporate production, investment, marketing, and management are restrained, and meanwhile, the cost of environmental governance will increase. Therefore, the profit margin becomes smaller, and the investment in R&D declines, which inhibits TI.

Alternatively, based on PH, ER has innovation compensation effect on TI (Porter & van der Linder, 1995; Jaffe & Palmer, 1997; Hart, 2004); that is, ER policies issued by government departments will stimulate corporate innovation activities, which can enhance corporate productivity and competitiveness. Under strict ER, firms will consider to increase R&D investment, and use advanced technology to reduce environmental pollution. The production of cleaner and green products can increase corporate profits.

Overall, ER has different effects, including *investment crowding-out effect* and *innovation compensation effect*. With the increase of intensity of ER, coal mining firms will attempt to meet environmental standards, and *investment crowding-out effect* lags behind *innovation compensation effect* (Cao et al., 2017). In addition, when coal mining firms are restricted by weak ER, the profits gained by the firms to increase products yield may be able to compensate for the losses caused by complying with ER. Meanwhile, with the increase of intensity of ER, consumers are more inclined to cleaner and green products, which will force high polluting firms to withdraw from the market. Confronted with the fierce market competition, the best strategy is to carry out TI activities, and thus achieve the goal of enhancing competitiveness.

In the end, drawing on the theoretical discussion mentioned above, we propose the following research hypotheses.

H₁: There is a U-shaped correlation between government ER and TI of coal mining firms; that is, the government ER has a threshold effect on the TI of coal mining firms.

ER policies can be viewed as a formal external supervision mechanism for the external uneconomical behavior of enterprises' economic activities with the function of supervision and restraint, while MA also plays a role in the supervision and control of environmental pollution caused by enterprises' economic activities. Therefore, compared with ER policies, MA can be considered as an informal external supervision mechanism. To be specific, MA, also known as media exposure rate, refers to the coverage of events through newspapers, television and other carriers, thus exerting a certain influence on the thoughts and behaviors of stakeholders (Fombrun & Shanley, 1990; Fiss & Zajac, 2006). According to the existing studies on media, media report has the functions of information transmission, public opinion guidance, image building and so on. First of all, concerning the information transmission function of the media, the economic activities of enterprises are transmitted to the stakeholders through newspapers, television and other tools, which reduces the information asymmetry among the stakeholders (Shen & Li, 2010). At the same time, in the process of information transmission, information is also interpreted (Dyck & Zingales, 2008; Bushee et al., 2010), which can not only arouse the attention of stakeholders to corporate behavior, but also deepen their understanding. For example, when an environmental pollution event of an enterprise is reported, the stakeholders may change the original trading behavior under the influence of the media, thus transmitting a negative market signal to the future operating conditions of the enterprise. Moreover, this

kind of instruction function of the media report is also conducive to the government departments to more comprehensively and deeply understand the behavior, making the policy formulation more in line with the reality. Second, the media have public opinion guiding function (Fang et al., 2009; Luo, 2012). In the research on communication, most scholars emphasize that media reports will have a far-reaching impact on public opinion (Kiousis, 2004). For example, there is a significant positive relationship between the public's attention to an event and the number of media reports. Especially at present, China's economy is in the period of transformation and reform, and the relevant mandatory legal mechanism needs to be further improved. In this social background, media reports are easy to cause public opinion pressure, which not only helps to promote the government departments to take administrative measures (such as notice of criticism, fines, etc.) for enterprises' environmental pollution behaviors, but also may force enterprises to modify their decision-making plans to environmental standards (such as innovative production technology level or marketing model, etc.). Finally, the media have the image building function (Godfrey, 2005; Barber & Odean, 2008; Lauterbach, 2017). For example, positive media reports on innovation and R&D activities of enterprises can help enterprises establish a good reputation in the hearts of stakeholders, which strengthens the endogenous power of enterprise innovation and development. As for the bad press of media, considering that the negative news itself is easy to attract attention and acts as a magnifying glass (Miller, 2006; Chen, 2010), polluters may be punished more severely. Under the dual effects of public opinion pressure and administrative sanction pressure, enterprises are more likely to rely on TI to achieve ECER³. In addition, considering China's historical and cultural environment, media reports are often policy-based. This implicit policy constraint has become an important mechanism to make up for the failure of government ER policies, and has increased the enthusiasm of firms to participate in policy-oriented activities. In the light of the above theoretical discussion, the following research hypotheses are proposed in our study.

H₂: MA plays a moderating role in the correlation between ER intensity and TI capability of coal mining firms.

Research design

Variable selection and variable definition

First, the capability of TI is one of the basic organizational capabilities that an enterprise should possess. The existing research mainly measures TI from the aspect of R&D investment, but the selection of proxy variable is too single to fully reflect the real situation of TI. Considering the long-term, cumulative and dynamic characteristics of TI, the study investigates innovation capability from three perspectives, including the input capability of TI, the output capability of TI and the transformation capability of TI. Specifically, we use the ratio of R&D expenses divided by the main business income to measure the input capability of TI. The output capability of TI of one coal enterprise is measured by the ratio of the number of patents granted by that of coal enterprise in year t divided by the number of patents granted by all coal mining firms in year t . We take the ratio of intangible assets divided by total assets as the proxy variable of TI transformation

³ ECER is the abbreviation for energy conservation and emission reduction.

ability.

Second, in order to reveal the differences of government ER tools more comprehensively, we divide ER into AER and EER. At the same time, based on the research purpose and the availability of data, this study uses the number of administrative regulations on environmental law issued by the local government to measure the intensity of AER, and uses the ratio of investment in environmental pollution control to GDP as an alternative indicator of EER intensity (Zhang et al., 2011). In the robustness test part, the intensity of AER is measured by the number of environmental administrative punishment cases in each region, and the ratio of sewage charges collected by each region to GDP is used as the proxy variable of EER intensity again.

Third, this paper uses newspapers and the Internet to collect the data of MA, that is, using CNKI China's important newspapers full-text database and *Baidu news search engine* to search the reports with company name in the title by year. MA, positive media reports and negative media reports are used to measure MA of coal listed companies, and the positive media reports and negative media reports are distinguished by text analysis and full text reading. Specifically, when we input the abbreviation of Listed Companies in the title column of CNKI China's major newspapers full text database, we can automatically retrieve the number of annual environmental news reports. Meanwhile, positive and negative media reports are identified according to the positive and negative keywords (negative keywords such as pollution, violation, over-standard, smoke and dust, and positive keywords such as conservation, innovation, environmental protection, low carbon) as well as the author's attitude and tone. When a report contains two or more listed companies, it is classified as the news reports of the company with the largest number of times. Finally, the robustness test is carried out with MA indicators collected by *Baidu news search engine* in a similar way.

Fourth, in order to eliminate the impact effect of other variables on the research results, our study is consistent with the existing studies, and controls the size, age (maturity), growth, leverage ratio, fixed assets ratio and ownership of enterprises.

In addition, the fixed-year effect is also controlled in this study, and the specific definitions of various variables are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Definition of main variables

Variable types	Names	Symbols	Computing methods
Dependent variables	TI input capability	TIIC	R & D expenses divided by main business income
	TI output capability	TIOC	Number of authorized patents
	TI transformation capability	TITC	Intangible assets divided by total assets
Independent variables	AER	GOV_ER	Number of administrative rules and regulations on environmental legal

Variable types	Names	Symbols	Computing methods
			work promulgated by local governments
	EER	ECO_ER	Environmental pollution control investment in each region divided by GDP
Moderating variables	MA	Media	Natural logarithm of the number of annual news reports plus 1
	Positive media coverage	Pos_Media	Natural logarithm of the number of positive news reports plus 1
	Negative media coverage	Neg_Media	Natural logarithm of the number of negative news reports plus 1
Control variables	Size	Lnsizes	Natural logarithm of total assets
	Age	Age	The number of years from the date of establishment of the enterprise to the end of the current period of the selected sample
	Growth	Growth	Year-on-year growth rate of net profit
	Leverage ratio	Lever	Total liabilities divided by total assets
	Fixed assets ratio	Asset	Total fixed assets divided by total assets
	Ownership	Owner	According to the ownership difference, it is divided into state-owned companies and non-state-owned companies. The value of state-owned companies is 1, otherwise it is 0.
	Year	Year	Taking 2016 as the base year, six annual dummy variables are set.

Notes: All financial indicators are compiled and calculated by hand.

Sample selection and data sources

The study takes listed companies in the coal industry of China's Shenzhen and Shanghai Stock Exchanges from 2016 to 2022 as the research sample. Based on the research variables determined and the existing domestic and foreign relevant studies, the sample data of this study is mainly collected in the following ways.

To be specific, the relevant data of TI comes from the *State Intellectual Property Office* and the annual financial reports disclosed by companies. The relevant data of ER are obtained from *China Statistical Yearbook and China Environmental Statistical Yearbook*. The relevant data of MA come from full text database of Chinese important newspapers in CNKI and *Baidu news search engine*. The relevant data of control variables are from CSMAR database, RESSET database, Sina Finance website, etc. All data are collected and calculated manually to obtain the required financial indicators. We select these firms through the following steps. (1) We exclude the samples of ST and *ST coal mining firms (*Special Treatment*, that is, the financial conditions of these firms are abnormal), and then

we exclude the samples of insolvent companies; (2) We remove the samples of missing and incorrect variable data. To eliminate the influence of outliers, all continuous variables are winsorized at the 1st and 99th percentiles. Finally, we obtain the sample data that consist of 38 coal mining firms.

We excluded data from non-listed companies. Because non-listed companies do not have publicly disclosed financial statements, we cannot search for information about non-listed companies.

We selected listed companies in the coal mining industry as the research sample, mainly considering that the coal mining industry is highly polluting and therefore more susceptible to environmental policies. We also did not select enterprises in other industries as research samples, because other industries are quite different from the coal industry, and we believe that the value of comparative research is low.

When the stock name of a listed company is labeled with ST or *ST, it indicates that the securities exchange has issued a risk warning. * ST is a warning of mandatory termination risk, abbreviated as "delisting risk warning". ST is a warning of the existence of other significant risks. These companies have issues with extreme values in their financial data. Therefore, in order to make the research results more reliable, we excluded these companies.

The website address of *Baidu news search engine* is <https://www.baidu.com/>.

The website address of CNKI China's major newspapers full text database is <https://kns.cnki.net/kns8s/?classid=MPMFIG1A>.

Model specification

According to the previous theoretical discussion, we construct the models (1) and (2) to verify the correlation between government ER intensity and TI of coal mining firms, and the impact of MA. The government ER intensity (the independent variable) is used as the core explanatory variable. Model (1) is used to confirm the correlation between government ER intensity and TI of coal mining firms, and model (2) is to verify the moderating effect of MA on the correlation. Figure 1 presents the model of moderating effect.

$$TIC(TIOC, TITC) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GOV_ER(ECO_ER) + \alpha_2 GOV_ER^2(ECO_ER^2) + \alpha_3 Lnsize + \alpha_4 Age + \alpha_5 Growth + \alpha_6 Lever + \alpha_7 Asset + \alpha_8 Owner + \sum Year + \varepsilon_1 \quad (1)$$

$$TIC(TIOC, TITC) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GOV_ER(ECO_ER) + \beta_2 GOV_ER^2(ECO_ER^2) + \beta_3 Media(Pos_Media, Neg_Media) + \beta_4 GOV_ER(ECO_ER) \times Media(Pos_Media, Neg_Media) + \beta_5 GOV_ER^2(ECO_ER^2) \times Media(Pos_Media, Neg_Media) + \beta_6 Lnsize + \beta_7 Age + \beta_8 Growth + \beta_9 Lever + \beta_{10} Asset + \beta_{11} Owner + \sum Year + \varepsilon_2 \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Moderating Effect

Empirical research

Analysis of empirical results

Table 2. Descriptive statistical results and correlation coefficients between main variables

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation	Min.	Max.	TIIC	TIOC	TITC	GOV ER	ECO ER	Media	Pos. Media	Neg. Media
TIIC	0.0216	0.3517	0	0.1048	1							
TIOC	0.4641	132.0813	0	0.7975	0.0128*	1						
TITC	0.1058	4.0357	0.0025	0.6049	0.0002	0.1307**	1					
GOV ER	6.1940	24.55	0	23	0.0506	-0.0773**	-0.2011***	1				
ECO ER	0.0194	0.0083	0.0053	0.0403	0.0307**	0.2905***	0.0221	0.1427*	1			
Media	1.9062	15.9947	0	2.6391	0.1051**	0.1103	0.0802	0.0320	0.1005*	1		
Pos. Media	0.8501	20.0670	0	1.0796	-0.0406	0.0104	0.0155	0.0518***	0.0017	0.0159	1	
Neg. Media	1.0966	13.3308	0	1.6480	0.1207***	0.0059	0.0621**	0.0902*	0.0544**	0.1044**	-0.1036	1

Notes: *, **, and *** respectively indicate at the 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels.

Firm size, age, growth, leverage, the fixed asset ratio, ownership, and year dummy are included in all regressions, but the detailed analysis is not reported for brevity.

Table 2 reveals descriptive statistical results and the correlation coefficients between main variables for the sample of coal mining firms during the period 2016-2022. As for the descriptive statistical results of variables, the mean value of TIIC of the sample enterprises is 0.0216, and the mean value of TIOC is 0.4641. We also find that the mean value of TITC is 0.1058. The difference of TIOC among sample enterprises is the most obvious, that is, the minimum value is 0, and the maximum value is 0.7975. In the process of statistics, we find that the sample enterprise with the largest number of authorized patents, that is, the strongest TIOC is China Shenhua Energy Co., Ltd. In the statistics of ER data, we find that the maximum intensity of AER of sample enterprises is 23, and its region is Beijing. In addition, the maximum intensity of EER is 0.0403, and its region is Shanxi Province. In the statistics of MA variables, the average of MA is 1.9062, the average of positive MA is 0.8501, and the average of negative MA is 1.0966, which indicates that, on the whole, the sample enterprises have more negative media reports.

In addition, according to the Pearson correlation coefficients between variables, we find that the correlation between the ER intensity and the TI capability is uncertain. Specifically, AER intensity has no significant correlation with TIIC, but has a significant negative correlation with TIOC and TITC. The intensity of EER is positively correlated with TIIC and TIOC, but not significantly correlated with TITC. Therefore, we have reason to believe that there is not a simple linear relationship between the intensity of

government ER and the TI capability of coal mining firms. Meanwhile, we find that the largest correlation coefficient between variables in Table 2 is between EER and TIOC, with a value of 0.2905. Combined with the correlation coefficients among other variables, we find that the values of each coefficient are lower than the threshold value of multicollinearity commonly considered by academia (0.60). Therefore, the test of correlation coefficients between main variables in this paper excludes the possibility of multicollinearity.

Table 3. The correlation between ER intensity and TI capability

Variables	TIIC		TIOC		TITC	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
GOV_ER	0.0301** (2.17)		-0.1014** (-2.79)		-0.2530*** (-6.02)	
GOV_ER ²	0.0244 (1.20)		0.0054 (0.06)		0.1041*** (4.08)	
ECO_ER		-0.2073*** (-5.58)		-0.1604** (-2.39)		0.0356* (2.04)
ECO_ER ²		0.1902** (2.56)		0.1105** (2.60)		0.0072 (0.06)
Lnsize	-0.1064*** (-5.06)	-0.1055*** (-5.47)	-0.0905** (-2.40)	-0.1408*** (-6.03)	-0.1004** (-2.55)	-0.1002** (-2.37)
Age	-0.0301** (-2.38)	-0.0294** (-2.45)	-0.0072 (-0.35)	-0.0105 (-1.07)	-0.1033** (-2.82)	-0.1030** (-2.82)
Growth	0.2006*** (3.77)	0.1802*** (3.22)	0.1091** (2.49)	0.1500** (2.53)	0.1233*** (5.25)	0.1193** (2.51)
Lever	-0.0372* (-1.95)	-0.0311* (-2.02)	-0.0128* (-1.89)	-0.0052 (-1.04)	-0.0148** (-2.25)	-0.0350* (-2.22)
Asset	0.0061 (0.02)	0.0107 (1.38)	0.0211* (1.99)	0.0040 (0.02)	0.0007 (1.03)	0.0036 (0.01)
Owner	0.1004** (2.67)	0.1051** (2.78)	0.0779** (2.36)	0.0744** (2.88)	0.1016*** (3.13)	0.1010*** (3.42)
Constant	0.1047*** (4.53)	0.1204*** (4.76)	0.1108*** (4.50)	0.1075*** (3.86)	0.1099*** (3.93)	0.1120*** (4.16)
R ²	0.3577	0.3480	0.3007	0.4505	0.4049	0.4660
F-Statistic	13.94	14.02	13.56	20.06	17.81	17.24

Notes: *, **, and *** respectively indicate at the 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels, and t-statistics are reported in parentheses.

Table 3 describes the results of the correlation between ER and TI. Columns (1) and (2) respectively test the correlation between AER intensity, EER intensity and TIIC. Columns (3) and (4) respectively test the relationship between AER intensity, EER intensity and TIOC. Columns (5) and (6) respectively test the relationship between AER intensity, EER intensity and TITC. The results show that AER and its quadratic term have no significant influence on TIIC. However, there is a significant negative correlation between EER intensity and TIIC, and there is a significant positive correlation between

the quadratic term of EER intensity and TIIC. The above results show that the correlation between EER intensity and TIIC is not a simple linear relationship, but a U-shaped relationship.

Additionally, there is a significant negative relationship between AER intensity and TIOC, but there is no significant relationship between the quadratic term of AER intensity and TIOC. In addition, there is a significant negative relationship between EER intensity and TIOC, and a significant positive relationship between the quadratic term of EER intensity and TIOC. The above results show that there is a simple linear relationship between AER intensity and TIOC, and when AER intensity is greater, the inhibiting effect on TIOC of coal mining firms will be stronger. At the same time, it indicates that the correlation between EER intensity and TIIC is not a simple linear relationship, but a U-shaped relationship.

Finally, the correlation between AER intensity and TITC is statistically significantly negative, and the correlation between the quadratic term of AER intensity and TITC is significantly positive. However, there is a significant positive correlation between EER intensity and TITC, while there is no significant correlation between the quadratic term of EER intensity and TITC. The above results show that the correlation between AER intensity and TITC is not a simple linear relationship, but a U-shaped relationship. At the same time, it shows that there is a simple linear relationship between EER intensity and TITC, and when EER intensity is greater, the promoting effect on TITC of coal mining firms will be stronger.

Table 4 presents the test results of the moderating effect of MA. There is a significant positive correlation between AER intensity and TIIC, and there is a significant positive correlation between $GOV_ER \times Media$ and TIIC. It indicates that with the increase of MA to environmental issues, the positive impact of AER intensity on TIIC is strengthened. The correlation between EER intensity and TIIC is statistically significantly negative, and there is a significant negative correlation between TIIC and $ECO_ER \times Media$. There is a significant positive correlation between the quadratic term of EER intensity and TIIC, and there is a significant positive correlation between TIIC and $ECO_ER2 \times Media$. It indicates that with the increase of MA to environmental issues, the non-linear influences of EER intensity on TIIC are strengthened. In other words, MA enhances the U-shaped relationship between EER intensity and TIIC. Similarly, MA enhances the U-shaped relationship between EER and TIOC. Finally, the correlation between AER intensity and TITC is statistically significantly negative. Moreover, there is a significant negative correlation between $GOV_ER \times Media$ and TITC. It indicates that with the increase of MA to environmental issues, the positive influence of AER intensity on TITC is strengthened.

Table 4. Moderating effect of MA

Variables	TIIC		TIOC		TITC	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
GOV_ER	0.0270** (2.62)		-0.0208*** (-3.89)		-0.1085*** (-5.24)	
GOV_ER2					0.0036 (1.31)	
GOV_ER×Media	0.1031*** (4.72)		-0.0074 (-1.01)		-0.0570*** (-4.88)	
GOV_ER2×Media					0.0692 (1.26)	
ECO_ER		-0.1905*** (-4.48)		-0.1087** (-2.40)		0.0274* (2.65)
ECO_ER2		0.1311*** (3.95)		0.0075* (2.01)		
ECO_ER×Media		-0.0583*** (-3.98)		-0.0495** (-2.37)		0.0054 (1.22)
ECO_ER2×Media		0.0144*** (3.82)		0.0053* (1.98)		
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	-0.1146*** (-3.72)	-0.1078*** (-3.69)	0.0913*** (3.44)	0.0985*** (3.50)	0.1304*** (5.07)	0.1226*** (5.02)
R2	0.2692	0.3085	0.2630	0.4001	0.2565	0.3307
F-Statistic	12.68***	13.58***	13.21***	14.45***	12.88***	11.67***

Notes: *, **, and *** respectively indicate at the 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels, and t-statistics are reported in parentheses.

Table 5 indicates the test results of the moderating effect of positive MA. From the perspective of the coefficient and significance level between variables, positive MA has a moderating effect on the correlation between AER intensity and TIOC. In other words, positive MA strengthens the negative impact of AER intensity on TIOC. In addition, EER intensity exerts a significant negative effect on TIIC. There is a significant negative correlation between ECO_ER×Pos_Media and TIIC. There is a significant positive correlation between the quadratic term of EER intensity and TIIC. There is a significant positive correlation between ECO_ER2×Pos_Media and TIIC. It suggests that with the increase of positive MA to environmental issues, the non-linear effects of EER intensity on TIIC are strengthened; that is, positive MA enhances the U-shaped relationship between EER intensity and TIIC. In addition, positive MA also strengthens the negative impact of EER intensity on TIOC.

Table 5. Moderating effect of positive MA

Variables	TIIC		TIOC		TITC	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
GOV_ER	0.0232** (2.47)		-0.0239*** (-5.19)		-0.0943*** (-4.50)	
GOV_ER2					0.0105 (1.02)	
GOV_ER×Pos_Media	0.0044 (1.50)		-0.0161 (-1.43)		-0.0047* (-2.08)	
GOV_ER2×Pos_Media					0.0038 (1.04)	
ECO_ER		-0.1509*** (-3.94)		-0.1433*** (-4.45)		0.0195* (2.38)
ECO_ER2		0.1098** (2.55)		0.0153* (2.20)		
ECO_ER×Pos_Media		-0.1084*** (-4.37)		-0.0261** (-2.40)		0.0067 (1.52)
ECO_ER2×Pos_Media		0.0504*** (3.58)		0.0103 (1.14)		
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	-0.0148*** (-4.70)	-0.0955*** (-3.73)	0.0803*** (4.07)	0.0916*** (3.49)	-0.004** (-2.26)	0.0233*** (4.46)
R2	0.2014	0.2780	0.3007	0.3048	0.2021	0.3024
F-Statistic	9.56***	14.93***	10.61***	13.44***	10.28***	11.76***

Notes: *, **, and *** respectively indicate at the 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels, and t-statistics are reported in parentheses.

Table 6 indicates the test results of the moderating effect of negative MA. From the perspective of the relationship coefficient and significance level between variables, there is a significant negative correlation between AER intensity and TIOC, and there is a significant negative correlation between GOV_ER×Neg_Media and TIIC, which indicates that negative MA strengthens the positive impact of AER intensity on TIOC.

EER intensity exerts a significant negative effect on TIIC. The coefficient of ECO_ER×Neg_Media is significantly negative. The quadratic term of EER intensity has a significant positive effect on TIIC. The correlation between ECO_ER2×Neg_Media and TIIC is statistically significantly positive.

It indicates that with the increase of negative media reports on environmental issues, the non-linear impacts of EER intensity on TIIC are strengthened. In other words, negative MA enhances the U-shaped relationship between EER intensity and TIIC. Similarly, negative MA enhances the U-shaped relationship between EER intensity and TIOC.

Table 6. Moderating effect of negative MA

Variables	TIIC		TIOC		TITC	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
GOV_ER	0.0308** (2.32)		-0.0227*** (-4.08)		-0.1026*** (-5.31)	
GOV_ER2					0.1157*** (4.96)	
GOV_ER×Neg_Media	0.0109 (0.56)		-0.0093** (-4.20)		-0.0042 (-1.01)	
GOV_ER2×Neg_Media					0.0030 (0.09)	
ECO_ER		-0.0515*** (-5.74)		-0.1207*** (-4.92)		0.0154** (2.28)
ECO_ER2		0.0781** (2.40)		0.0532** (1.97)		
ECO_ER×Neg_Media		-0.0189*** (-5.69)		-0.0211** (-2.48)		0.0001 (0.02)
ECO_ER2×Neg_Media		0.0471** (2.35)		0.0457*** (3.96)		
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	- 0.0150** * (-5.63)	-0.0363*** (-4.79)	0.0173*** (4.33)	0.0418*** (3.96)	-0.1074*** (-6.76)	0.0852** * (4.31)
R2	0.2105	0.3086	0.2108	0.3401	0.2748	0.3259
F-Statistic	14.06***	14.95***	12.75***	13.67***	9.46***	11.04***

Notes: *, **, and *** respectively indicate at the 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels, and t-statistics are reported in parentheses.

Further analysis

The empirical test results above show that ER has a non-linear effect on TI. Therefore, the panel threshold model proposed by Hansen (1999) is used in this study to investigate whether there is threshold effect in the process of ER intensity's influence on TI capability. In this study, environmental regulatory intensity is selected as the threshold variable, and the single threshold model is set as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 TIIC(TIOC, TITC) = & \eta_0 + \eta_1 GOV_ER(ECO_ER) I(P \leq r) + \eta_2 GOV_ER(ECO_ER) I(P > r) \\
 & + \eta_3 Lnsiz e + \eta_4 Age + \eta_5 Growth + \eta_6 Lever + \eta_7 Asset + \eta_8 Owner + \sum Year + \varepsilon_3
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

where R is the threshold value, and the threshold value of a single threshold model divides the observed value variable into two threshold intervals. η_1 and η_2 are the estimated coefficients of environmental regulatory intensity in different threshold intervals.

According to the research method of threshold effect proposed by scholars, whether there is threshold effect of ER intensity is determined. If there is threshold effect, the

threshold number and threshold value are further determined. The specific test results are listed in Table 7.

Table 7. Test results of threshold model

Dependent variables	Threshold variables	Threshold number	F-Statistic	P-Statistic	Sampling frequency	1%	5%	10%
TIIC	ECO_ER	Single threshold	15.0952**	0.0120	1000	6.2043	3.0894	2.7439
		Double threshold	2.4507	0.4380	1000	8.4055	3.2079	2.9071
		Triple threshold	2.3008	0.1086	1000	8.9306	3.4766	3.4607
TIOC	ECO_ER	Single threshold	15.2805***	0.0032	1000	14.7454	7.0977	3.3518
		Double threshold	0.7509	1.0000	1000	17.7742	13.3158	5.6627
		Triple threshold	13.8004	0.1242	1000	4.9700	15.8126	3.5321
TITC	GOV_ER	Single threshold	15.2864***	0.0010	1000	14.6056	8.2260	3.1003
		Double threshold	20.5713***	0.0000	1000	10.3767	8.9420	5.5693
		Triple threshold	3.4571	0.3075	1000	7.8998	5.3107	4.1568

Notes: *, **, and *** respectively indicate at the 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels.

Table 7 indicates the results of threshold effect test. In the self-sampling test of threshold effect, 1%, 5% and 10% are significance levels, respectively. According to the F value and P value of the test results, we find that when the explanatory variable is TIIC, the single threshold effect of EER intensity has passed the significance test at the 5% level, while the p value of double threshold and triple threshold is greater than 0.1. This shows that there is a single threshold value in the above panel threshold model; that is, when using EER intensity as a threshold variable, there is a single threshold value for the impact of EER intensity on TIIC. Then, when the explained variable is TIOC, the single threshold effect of EER intensity passes the significance test at 1% level, while the P values of double threshold and triple threshold are greater than 0.1. This test shows that there is a single threshold in the above panel threshold model; that is, when EER intensity is taken as the threshold variable, there is a single threshold value for the impact of EER intensity on TIOC. Finally, when the explained variable is TITC, the single threshold effect and double threshold effect of AER intensity pass the significance test at 1% level, while the p value of triple threshold is greater than 0.1. This test shows that the above panel threshold model has double threshold value; that is, when AER intensity is the threshold variable, the impact of AER intensity on TITC has double threshold value.

Endogeneity test

Considering the endogeneity problems of the sample selection bias and the mutual causality between variables, instrumental variable method is proposed to solve the above

problems.

Based on the research conclusions of Lin et al. (2011), we use the year-industry averages of ER of other coal mining companies as instrumental variables for the above indicators. This is mainly based on the following reasons. The external economic environment and industry characteristics faced by companies in the same industry and year are relatively similar, so these two quantitative indices of ER have a certain correlation with their respective instrumental variables. However, there is no evidence to suggest that ER of other coal mining companies in the same industry and year will affect the TI of the coal mining company, so these instrumental variables have exogeneity. In summary, the instrumental variables are appropriate.

According to the endogeneity test results, the statistics of Kleibergen-Paap rk LM and their p-values show that our results reject the null hypothesis of the under-identification of instrument variables at the 1% significance level. Moreover, the statistics of Kleibergen-Paap rk Wald F are much greater than the critical value (16.38) at the 10% level, which excludes the possibility of weak instruments in instrumental variables regression. The final test results reveal that the estimated coefficients and significance levels of each variable are basically consistent with the expectations, indicating that the above estimation results have a certain reliability.

Robustness test

In the section of robustness test, we perform additional tests to check the robustness of our study results.

First, the intensity of AER is measured by the number of environmental administrative punishment cases in each region, and the ratio of sewage charges collected by each region to GDP is used as the proxy variable of EER intensity. After the substitution of proxy variables, according to the model (1), the same regression method is used to test the impact of ER intensity on TI capability again, and the estimated results are basically consistent with the above research conclusions.

Second, the environmental news reports of sample enterprises collected by *Baidu news search engine* are used as proxy variables of MA. According to the model (2), the moderating effect of MA is tested again, and the results show that the estimation coefficients do not change significantly. Thus, our conclusions are robust and convincing.

Conclusions and policy recommendations

Conclusions

The traditional coal industry is facing severe challenges in the process of China's economic upgrading. The prominent problems such as backward production technology, extensive growth mode, overcapacity and serious environmental pollution restrict the development of coal mining firms. With the continuous deterioration of the production and operation situation of coal mining firms, TI has attracted great attention of enterprises, and TI strategy is recognized as the best development strategy in academic and practical circles. Innovation capability is the basic ability that enterprises should have for survival

and development. At the same time, the coal industry has been labeled with high energy consumption, high emission and high pollution. Effective prevention and control of environmental pollution caused by coal mining firms has become the key work of the relevant government departments. As the main measures of government departments to control the environmental pollution behavior of enterprises, ER will have a significant impact on the economic activities of coal mining firms. Therefore, whether the government's ER policy has an impact on the TI capability of coal mining firms has become the core issue of research.

On the other hand, as an informal external governance tool, the media has functions such as information transmission, public opinion guidance and image building. Therefore, MA may have a certain impact on the correlation between ER intensity and TI capability. Based on the above theoretical logic, this study takes listed companies in the coal industry of China's Shenzhen and Shanghai Stock Exchanges from 2016 to 2022 as the research object, empirically analyzes the relationship between ER intensity and TI capability, and further tests the influence of MA on the above-mentioned variable relationship.

There is a U-shaped correlation between EER intensity and TIIC, and there is a single threshold effect. There is a U-shaped correlation between EER intensity and TIOC, and there is a single threshold effect. There is a U-shaped relationship between intensity of AER and TITC, and there is a double threshold effect. In addition, MA enhances the correlation between ER intensity and TI capability, especially for negative MA, which has a more significant strengthening effect. This conclusion confirms that media environmental news reports play a role in environmental pollution prevention and control. The research conclusion provides new empirical evidence for the theoretical research of ER and TI, and has certain enlightenment significance for the reform and development of coal mining firms at the present stage.

Policy recommendations

In order to enhance the TI capability of coal mining firms, this study puts forward policy suggestions from the following aspects.

First, while the government departments implement merger and reorganization, integration and closure of the traditional coal industry, they should guide coal mining firms to attach importance to independent R&D⁴, and fully mobilize the enthusiasm and creativity of talents. They should not only make reasonable and effective evaluation of innovative achievements, but also assist enterprises to establish a feasible transformation mechanism of innovative achievements, so as to promote the development of coal mining firms. Coal mining firms should strengthen the practicality of TI, and use TI to expand the development space.

Second, government departments should strive to achieve the compliance and rational design of ER policy, so as to make ER policy play the greatest role in the prevention and control of environmental pollution and the positive incentive role for TI. The government can reduce the environmental pollution caused by raw coal mining, transportation,

⁴ R&D is the abbreviation for research and development.

processing and other processes through the binding force of ER, and promote coal mining firms to enter the road of green and low-carbon development.

Third, as an informal external governance mechanism, media environmental news reports play an important role in the prevention and control of environmental pollution, strengthening the impact of ER on TI to a certain extent. Therefore, the government departments should make full use of the media to carry out policy guidance on the operation and management activities of coal mining firms, so that enterprises can fundamentally and correctly understand the ER policies, especially the innovation benefits brought by appropriate ER, so as to enhance the willingness and endogenous power of corporate TI.

Fourth, based on the above research findings, we believe that ER policies have a non-negligible impact on the sustainable development of coal mining firms. Government departments should strengthen supervision of corporate behavior, obtain timely feedback on the effects of environmental policies, and adjust policies based on the actual situation of coal mining firms, in order to achieve the best results of policies. At the same time, government departments should pay attention to corporate behavior and establish the amount of pollutant discharge fees to be collected. For example, government departments and banks jointly build enterprise databases in areas such as pollution reduction, carbon reduction, and carbon emission reduction, providing support to coal mining firms with financing needs, promoting the investment of funds in clean energy, energy conservation, and environmental protection technology development fields, and thereby promoting the sustainable development of coal mining firms.

China is the largest coal market, but the theoretical research on the basic theory of the coal industry is relatively weak, and coal mining firms are also facing a serious development bottleneck. Although this study provides new insights for the management practice of coal mining firms and lays a theoretical foundation for the research of ER and TI in academic circles, there are still some limitations in this study. First of all, this study is based on the listed companies in the coal industry of China's Shenzhen and Shanghai Stock Exchanges, so it remains to be further discussed whether the research conclusions can also be applied to other countries. Second, this study examines the role of media environmental news reports in environmental pollution control. Therefore, future scholars need to make in-depth analysis on whether media news reports have other roles.

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